

A SQUARE-SPLITTING A -CONVOLUTION OF NARKIEWICZ TYPE

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Abstract

Motivated by Narkiewicz's divisor systems and the induced A -convolutions, we introduce an explicit divisor system arising from the canonical decomposition $n = u(n)v(n)^2$ with $u(n)$ squarefree. The resulting A -convolution \star splits the divisor structure into squarefree and square parts and yields a convolution algebra canonically isomorphic to a two-variable Dirichlet convolution. We develop the associated multiplicative theory: a closed formula for the \star -Möbius function, a sharp inversion principle, and Euler-product formulae for generalized divisor sums. We also define an Euler-type totient φ_\star by $\sum_{d \in A(n)} \varphi_\star(d) = n$ and obtain an explicit prime-power description. Moreover, we establish an effective asymptotic formula for $\sum_{n \leq x} \varphi_\star(n)$, whose leading constant is given by an absolutely convergent Euler product. We further derive a sharp asymptotic formula for $\sum_{n \leq x} \tau_\star(n)$ and determine the natural density of the support of μ_\star . Numerical examples illustrate the identities and the predicted constants.

1. Introduction

Let \mathcal{A} denote the complex vector space of arithmetic functions $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$. The classical Dirichlet convolution is

$$(f * g)(n) = \sum_{d|n} f(d)g(n/d),$$

with identity $\varepsilon(1) = 1$ and $\varepsilon(n) = 0$ for $n > 1$. Narkiewicz introduced a far-reaching generalization by restricting the divisor sum to a divisor system $A(n) \subseteq \{d : d \mid n\}$ and studying when the induced operation

$$(f *_A g)(n) = \sum_{d \in A(n)} f(d)g(n/d),$$

behaves regularly, namely in the sense of associativity, preservation of multiplicativity, and an inversion theory [5]. This initiated a broad literature on regular convolutions and related Euler-type functions [5, 4, 7, 1].

In this paper, we propose a computable A -divisor system built from the canonical decomposition $n = u(n)v(n)^2$ [4], where $u(n)$ is squarefree and $v(n)$ records the square part. This yields a regular convolution \star which is canonically isomorphic to a two-variable Dirichlet convolution via the transform $Tf(u, v) = f(uv^2)$. The bivariate model gives an explicit inversion theory. In particular, it provides a closed formula for the \star -Möbius function μ_\star , and leads to new Euler-type functions, including a totient φ_\star characterized by $\sum_{d \in A(n)} \varphi_\star(d) = n$, with a computable mean-value constant and summatory asymptotics.

2. A Square–Splitting Divisor System

Definition 1. For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, define $u(n), v(n) \in \mathbb{N}$ by the unique factorization

$$n = u(n)v(n)^2,$$

where $u(n)$ is squarefree. Equivalently, if $n = \prod_p p^{\nu_p(n)}$, then

$$u(n) = \prod_{p: \nu_p(n) \text{ odd}} p, \quad v(n) = \prod_p p^{\lfloor \nu_p(n)/2 \rfloor}.$$

Remark 1. Write every $n \geq 1$ uniquely as

$$n = u(n)v(n)^2,$$

where $u(n)$ is squarefree. Then the divisor system

$$A(n) = \{u_1 v_1^2 : u_1 \mid u(n), v_1 \mid v(n)\}$$

may be viewed as the set of lattice points in the product poset

$$\mathcal{L}(n) := \text{Div}(u(n)) \times \text{Div}(v(n)),$$

ordered by $(u_1, v_1) \preceq (u_2, v_2)$ if and only if $u_1 \mid u_2$ and $v_1 \mid v_2$. Equivalently, the map

$$(u_1, v_1) \mapsto u_1 v_1^2$$

is a bijection from $\mathcal{L}(n)$ onto $A(n)$. In this sense, the \star -convolution is the incidence convolution on the two-coordinate divisor lattice $\mathcal{L}(n)$: the factorization $n = a \star b$ corresponds to choosing a decomposition

$$u(n) = u(a)u(b), \quad v(n) = v(a)v(b),$$

where $\gcd(u(a), u(b)) = 1$. Equivalently, it provides a partition of the prime support of $u(n)$ between $u(a)$ and $u(b)$, while the v -coordinate corresponds to splitting prime exponents in $v(n)$. In particular, $\gcd(v(a), v(b))$ need not be 1 in general. This viewpoint yields an immediate counting interpretation of τ_\star . Indeed,

$$\tau_\star(n) = \#A(n) = \#\mathcal{L}(n) = d(u(n))d(v(n)),$$

so $\tau_\star(n)$ counts the number of pairs (u_1, v_1) with $u_1 \mid u(n)$ and $v_1 \mid v(n)$, that is, the number of divisor choices in the two independent coordinates [4]. Moreover, $\tau_\star(n)$ also counts the number of ordered \star -factorizations $n = a \star b$, equivalently, the number of ordered decompositions of the pair $(u(n), v(n))$ into two coordinatewise factors. Thus, the arithmetic of the \star -convolution is governed by a natural product-poset combinatorics coming from the squarefree-square splitting.

Theorem 1. *Define, for each n , the set*

$$A(n) := \{d = u_1v_1^2 : u_1 \mid u(n), v_1 \mid v(n)\}.$$

Then the following statements hold:

1. *$A(n)$ is a divisor system: $1, n \in A(n)$ and every $d \in A(n)$ divides n ,*
2. *A is multiplicative in the strong sense: if $\gcd(m, n) = 1$, then*

$$A(mn) = \{ab : a \in A(m), b \in A(n)\},$$

3. *The counting function $\tau_\star(n) := |A(n)|$ satisfies*

$$\tau_\star(n) = d(u(n))d(v(n)) = 2^{\omega(u(n))}d(v(n)),$$

where d is the classical divisor function and ω counts distinct prime factors.

Proof. If $d = u_1v_1^2$ with $u_1 \mid u(n)$ and $v_1 \mid v(n)$, then $u_1 \mid u(n)$ and $v_1^2 \mid v(n)^2$, and hence, $d \mid u(n)v(n)^2 = n$. The choices $u_1 = 1, v_1 = 1$ and $u_1 = u(n), v_1 = v(n)$ give $1, n \in A(n)$.

If $\gcd(m, n) = 1$, then $u(mn) = u(m)u(n)$ and $v(mn) = v(m)v(n)$, and divisors split uniquely across coprime components. Thus, $u_1 \mid u(mn)$ if and only if $u_1 = u_{1m}u_{1n}$ with $u_{1m} \mid u(m)$ and $u_{1n} \mid u(n)$, and similarly, $v_1 = v_{1m}v_{1n}$ with $v_{1m} \mid v(m)$ and $v_{1n} \mid v(n)$. Hence, $A(mn) = \{(u_{1m}v_{1m}^2)(u_{1n}v_{1n}^2)\}$, as claimed.

Since $u(n)$ is squarefree, $d(u(n)) = 2^{\omega(u(n))}$. Also, the map $(u_1, v_1) \mapsto u_1v_1^2$ is injective because u_1 captures the parity of exponents and v_1 captures the square part. Therefore, $|A(n)| = d(u(n))d(v(n))$. □

Definition 2. For arithmetic functions f and g , define

$$(f \star g)(n) := \sum_{d \in A(n)} f(d)g(n/d),$$

where $A(n)$ is given in Theorem 1.

Theorem 2. Let \mathcal{A} be the space of arithmetic functions. Then (\mathcal{A}, \star) is a commutative ring with identity ε . Moreover, the bivariate function

$$\mathcal{T}f(u, v) := f(uv^2),$$

where u is squarefree and $v \in \mathbb{N}$, is a ring isomorphism between (\mathcal{A}, \star) and the bivariate Dirichlet convolution ring

$$(F \odot G)(u, v) := \sum_{u_1|u} \sum_{v_1|v} F(u_1, v_1)G(u/u_1, v/v_1),$$

defined on the domain $\{(u, v) : u \text{ is squarefree}\}$.

Proof. Commutativity is immediate from the symmetric summand $f(d)g(n/d)$. The identity ε satisfies $(f \star \varepsilon)(n) = f(n)$ because only the term $d = n$ contributes.

For associativity, use the bivariate model. Fix n and write $n = uv^2$ with u squarefree. By Theorem 1, the elements of $A(n)$ are in bijection with pairs (u_1, v_1) with $u_1 | u$ and $v_1 | v$. Thus,

$$(f \star g)(uv^2) = \sum_{u_1|u} \sum_{v_1|v} f(u_1v_1^2)g\left(\frac{u}{u_1} \left(\frac{v}{v_1}\right)^2\right) = (\mathcal{T}f \odot \mathcal{T}g)(u, v).$$

Hence, $\mathcal{T}(f \star g) = \mathcal{T}f \odot \mathcal{T}g$. Associativity and distributivity for \star follow from the corresponding properties of \odot , which is the standard Dirichlet convolution on the product lattice of divisors in two coordinates. Finally, \mathcal{T} is bijective since every n is uniquely of the form uv^2 with u squarefree. \square

Corollary 1. If f and g are multiplicative, then $f \star g$ is multiplicative.

Proof. Under \mathcal{T} , multiplicativity corresponds to Euler factorization over primes in each coordinate, and the product form in the second statement of Theorem 1 yields the standard factorization argument over coprime components. \square

3. Möbius Theory and Inversion

Definition 3. Let $\mathbf{1}$ denote the constant function $\mathbf{1}(n) \equiv 1$. The \star -Möbius function μ_\star is the \star -inverse of $\mathbf{1}$. That is,

$$\mu_\star \star \mathbf{1} = \varepsilon.$$

Theorem 3. For all n ,

$$\mu_\star(n) = \mu(u(n))\mu(v(n)),$$

where μ is the classical Möbius function and $n = u(n)v(n)^2$. In particular, for prime powers p^k ,

$$\mu_\star(p^k) = \begin{cases} -1, & k = 1 \text{ or } 2, \\ +1, & k = 3, \\ 0, & k \geq 4. \end{cases}$$

Moreover, the Dirichlet generating series admits the Euler product

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\mu_\star(n)}{n^s} = \prod_p (1 - p^{-s} - p^{-2s} + p^{-3s}) = \frac{1}{\zeta(s)\zeta(2s)},$$

where $\Re(s) > 1$.

Proof. Work in the bivariate model of Theorem 2. The inverse of the constant function $\mathbf{1}(uv^2) = 1$ under \odot is $(u, v) \mapsto \mu(u)\mu(v)$, since

$$\sum_{u_1|u} \sum_{v_1|v} \mu(u_1)\mu(v_1) = \varepsilon(u)\varepsilon(v),$$

by the usual one-variable identity $\sum_{d|n} \mu(d) = \varepsilon(n)$ [4] applied in each coordinate. Transporting back via \mathcal{T}^{-1} yields $\mu_\star(n) = \mu(u(n))\mu(v(n))$.

For prime powers, if $k = 2b$ is even, then $u(p^k) = 1$ and $v(p^k) = p^b$. Hence, $\mu_\star(p^{2b}) = \mu(p^b)$, which equals -1 for $b = 1$ and 0 for $b \geq 2$. If $k = 2b + 1$ is odd, then $u(p^k) = p$ and $v(p^k) = p^b$, giving $\mu_\star(p^{2b+1}) = \mu(p)\mu(p^b) = (-1)\mu(p^b)$. Hence, -1 for $b = 0$, $+1$ for $b = 1$, and 0 for $b \geq 2$.

The Euler product follows from multiplicativity and the prime-power values:

$$\sum_{k \geq 0} \frac{\mu_\star(p^k)}{p^{ks}} = 1 - \frac{1}{p^s} - \frac{1}{p^{2s}} + \frac{1}{p^{3s}} = (1 - p^{-s})(1 - p^{-2s}).$$

Multiplying over primes yields

$$\prod_p (1 - p^{-s}) \prod_p (1 - p^{-2s}) = \frac{1}{\zeta(s)\zeta(2s)}.$$

□

Theorem 4. For arithmetic functions f and F , the following are equivalent:

$$F(n) = \sum_{d \in A(n)} f(d) \quad \text{for all } n \quad \text{if and only if} \quad f(n) = \sum_{d \in A(n)} \mu_\star(d)F(n/d) \quad \text{for all } n.$$

Equivalently, $F = \mathbf{1} \star f$ if and only if $f = \mu_\star \star F$.

Proof. This is the standard convolution inversion. If $F = \mathbf{1} \star f$, then convolving both sides by μ_\star gives $\mu_\star \star F = (\mu_\star \star \mathbf{1}) \star f = \varepsilon \star f = f$. The converse follows in the same way. \square

Theorem 5. *Let f be multiplicative with $f(1) \neq 0$. Then f is \star -invertible. That is, there exists $f^{(-1)\star}$ such that $f \star f^{(-1)\star} = \varepsilon$, and the \star -inverse is multiplicative. On prime powers, writing $g = f^{(-1)\star}$, one has the recursion*

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} f(p^{2j})g(p^{k-2j}) + \mathbf{1}_{k \text{ odd}} \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor} f(p^{2j+1})g(p^{k-(2j+1)}) = \varepsilon(p^k),$$

where $\mathbf{1}_{k \text{ odd}}$ is 1 if k is odd and 0 otherwise. In particular,

$$\begin{aligned} g(1) &= 1/f(1), \\ g(p) &= -\frac{f(p)}{f(1)^2}, \\ g(p^2) &= -\frac{f(p^2)}{f(1)^2}, \\ g(p^3) &= \frac{2f(p)f(p^2) - f(p^3)f(1)}{f(1)^3}, \end{aligned}$$

and for $k \geq 4$ the values are determined uniquely by the recursion.

Proof. Transport to the bivariate ring. Under \mathcal{T} , invertibility in \star is equivalent to invertibility in \odot . For multiplicative f with $f(1) \neq 0$, invertibility in the Dirichlet-type convolution follows prime by prime by a standard triangular recursion on the divisor lattice, and the inverse is multiplicative. The displayed recursion is exactly the prime-power specialization of $(f \star g)(p^k) = \varepsilon(p^k)$ using the description of $A(p^k)$: if $k = 2b$ is even then $A(p^{2b}) = \{p^0, p^2, \dots, p^{2b}\}$, while if $k = 2b + 1$ is odd then $A(p^{2b+1})$ contains all p^0, \dots, p^{2b+1} . The explicit formulas for small k follow by solving the first few triangular equations. \square

4. Generalized Divisor Sums and an Euler-Type Totient

4.1. \star -Divisor Sums

For $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$ define

$$\sigma_{\star, \alpha}(n) := \sum_{d \in A(n)} d^\alpha, \quad \tau_\star(n) = \sigma_{\star, 0}(n) = |A(n)|.$$

Theorem 6. *Let $n = u(n)v(n)^2$. Then for every $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$,*

$$\sigma_{\star, \alpha}(n) = \sigma_\alpha(u(n)) \sigma_{2\alpha}(v(n)),$$

where σ_β is the classical divisor sum $\sigma_\beta(m) = \sum_{d|m} d^\beta$. In particular, $\sigma_{*,\alpha}$ is multiplicative and for prime powers we have

$$\sigma_{*,\alpha}(p^{2b}) = 1 + p^{2\alpha} + \dots + p^{2b\alpha}, \quad \sigma_{*,\alpha}(p^{2b+1}) = (1 + p^\alpha)(1 + p^{2\alpha} + \dots + p^{2b\alpha}).$$

Moreover, the Dirichlet series of $\sigma_{*,\alpha}$ has Euler factor

$$\sum_{k \geq 0} \frac{\sigma_{*,\alpha}(p^k)}{p^{ks}} = \frac{1 + p^{-s} + p^{-(s-\alpha)}}{(1 - p^{-2s})(1 - p^{-(2s-2\alpha)})},$$

and hence

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\sigma_{*,\alpha}(n)}{n^s} = \zeta(2s)\zeta(2s - 2\alpha) \prod_p \left(1 + p^{-s} + p^{-(s-\alpha)}\right),$$

with absolute convergence in the right half-plane. In particular, it is absolutely convergent for $\Re(s) > \max\{1, 1 + \Re(\alpha)\}$.

Proof. By Theorem 1, each $d \in A(n)$ is uniquely of the form $d = u_1 v_1^2$ with $u_1 \mid u(n)$ and $v_1 \mid v(n)$. Therefore,

$$\sigma_{*,\alpha}(n) = \sum_{u_1 \mid u(n)} \sum_{v_1 \mid v(n)} (u_1 v_1^2)^\alpha \tag{1}$$

$$= \left(\sum_{u_1 \mid u(n)} u_1^\alpha \right) \left(\sum_{v_1 \mid v(n)} v_1^{2\alpha} \right) \tag{2}$$

$$= \sigma_\alpha(u(n)) \sigma_{2\alpha}(v(n)). \tag{3}$$

The prime-power formulas follow by substituting $u(p^{2b}) = 1$, $v(p^{2b}) = p^b$ and $u(p^{2b+1}) = p$, $v(p^{2b+1}) = p^b$. Summing the resulting geometric series gives the rational Euler factor, and the Euler product follows from multiplicativity. \square

Definition 4. Define φ_* as the unique arithmetic function satisfying

$$\sum_{d \in A(n)} \varphi_*(d) = n,$$

for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Equivalently, $\varphi_* \star \mathbf{1} = \text{id}$, where $\text{id}(n) = n$.

Theorem 7. The function φ_* is multiplicative. For a prime p and $b \geq 1$,

$$\varphi_*(p^{2b}) = (p^2 - 1)p^{2b-2}, \quad \varphi_*(p^{2b+1}) = (p - 1)(p^2 - 1)p^{2b-2},$$

$\varphi_*(p) = p - 1$ and $\varphi_*(1) = 1$. Equivalently, for $n = u(n)v(n)^2$,

$$\varphi_*(n) = \varphi(u(n)) \cdot \left(v(n)^2 \prod_{p \mid v(n)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^2}\right) \right),$$

where φ is the classical Euler totient.

Proof. Uniqueness follows since $\mathbf{1}$ is \star -invertible and $\varphi_\star = \text{id} \star \mu_\star$. Multiplicativity follows from Corollary 1. For prime powers, use the defining relation. If $k = 2b$ is even, then $A(p^{2b}) = \{p^0, p^2, \dots, p^{2b}\}$, so

$$\varphi_\star(1) + \varphi_\star(p^2) + \dots + \varphi_\star(p^{2b}) = p^{2b}.$$

Subtracting the same identity for $b - 1$ gives

$$\varphi_\star(p^{2b}) = p^{2b} - p^{2b-2} = (p^2 - 1)p^{2b-2}.$$

If $k = 2b + 1$ is odd, then $A(p^{2b+1}) = \{p^0, p^1, \dots, p^{2b+1}\}$, from which it follows that

$$\sum_{j=0}^{2b+1} \varphi_\star(p^j) = p^{2b+1}.$$

Splitting even and odd exponents, we obtain

$$\sum_{j=0}^b \varphi_\star(p^{2j}) + \sum_{j=0}^b \varphi_\star(p^{2j+1}) = p^{2b+1}.$$

But the even sum equals p^{2b} by the even-case identity, so

$$\sum_{j=0}^b \varphi_\star(p^{2j+1}) = p^{2b}(p - 1).$$

Subtracting the same identity for $b - 1$ yields, for $b \geq 1$,

$$\varphi_\star(p^{2b+1}) = p^{2b}(p - 1) - p^{2b-2}(p - 1) = (p - 1)(p^2 - 1)p^{2b-2}.$$

The factorized form in terms of $u(n)$ and $v(n)$ follows by multiplicativity and the prime-power formulas. \square

Theorem 8. *Let φ_\star be the Euler-type function defined by*

$$\sum_{d \in A(n)} \varphi_\star(d) = n,$$

for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then the constant

$$M := \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^2} + \frac{(p-1)^2}{p^5} \right)$$

converges absolutely, and for every $\varepsilon \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \varphi_\star(n) = \frac{M}{2} x^2 + O_\varepsilon(x^{1+\varepsilon}),$$

as $x \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof. Set

$$L(s, \varphi_\star) := \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\varphi_\star(n)}{n^s},$$

where $\Re(s) > 2$. A computation of the Euler factors, using the prime-power values from Theorem 7, gives the factorization

$$L(s, \varphi_\star) = \frac{\zeta(s-1)}{\zeta(s)} G(s), \quad G(s) := \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{p-1}{p^s(p^s+p)} \right), \quad (4)$$

where $G(s)$ converges absolutely for $\Re(s) > 1$. Write

$$G(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{g(n)}{n^s},$$

where $\Re(s) > 1$. Since $\zeta(s-1)/\zeta(s)$ is the Dirichlet series of Euler's totient function φ , Equation (4) implies that

$$\varphi_\star = \varphi * g$$

under the ordinary Dirichlet convolution. Hence, for $x \geq 2$,

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \varphi_\star(n) = \sum_{d \leq x} g(d) \sum_{k \leq x/d} \varphi(k).$$

Since the Dirichlet series for $G(s)$ converges absolutely for $\Re(s) > 1$, standard coefficient bounds imply that for every $\varepsilon \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$,

$$\sum_{n \leq t} |g(n)| \ll_\varepsilon t^{1+\varepsilon}.$$

By partial summation, this yields

$$\sum_{n \leq t} \frac{|g(n)|}{n} \ll_\varepsilon t^\varepsilon, \quad \sum_{n > t} \frac{|g(n)|}{n^2} \ll_\varepsilon t^{-1+\varepsilon}.$$

We use the effective asymptotic for the summatory totient [3]:

$$\sum_{k \leq y} \varphi(k) = \frac{1}{2\zeta(2)} y^2 + O\left(y(\log y)^{2/3} \max\left\{1, (\log \log y)^{1/3}\right\}\right),$$

for $y \geq 2$. Split the sum over d into the ranges $d \leq x/2$ and $x/2 < d \leq x$.

If $d \leq x/2$, then $x/d \geq 2$, so applying the above asymptotic with $y = x/d$ gives

$$\sum_{k \leq x/d} \varphi(k) = \frac{1}{2\zeta(2)} \left(\frac{x}{d}\right)^2 + O\left(\frac{x}{d} \left(\log \frac{x}{d}\right)^{2/3} \max\left\{1, \left(\log \log \frac{x}{d}\right)^{1/3}\right\}\right).$$

Therefore,

$$\sum_{d \leq x/2} g(d) \sum_{k \leq x/d} \varphi(k) = \frac{x^2}{2\zeta(2)} \sum_{d \leq x/2} \frac{g(d)}{d^2} + O\left(x(\log x)^{2/3} \max\{1, (\log \log x)^{1/3}\} \sum_{d \leq x/2} \frac{|g(d)|}{d}\right),$$

and hence,

$$\sum_{d \leq x/2} g(d) \sum_{k \leq x/d} \varphi(k) = \frac{x^2}{2\zeta(2)} \sum_{d \leq x/2} \frac{g(d)}{d^2} + O_\varepsilon(x^{1+\varepsilon}).$$

If $x/2 < d \leq x$, then $1 \leq x/d < 2$, so $\sum_{k \leq x/d} \varphi(k) \ll 1$. Thus,

$$\sum_{x/2 < d \leq x} g(d) \sum_{k \leq x/d} \varphi(k) \ll \sum_{x/2 < d \leq x} |g(d)| \ll_\varepsilon x^{1+\varepsilon}.$$

Combining the two ranges, we obtain

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \varphi_\star(n) = \frac{x^2}{2\zeta(2)} \sum_{d \leq x/2} \frac{g(d)}{d^2} + O_\varepsilon(x^{1+\varepsilon}).$$

Now,

$$\sum_{d \leq x/2} \frac{g(d)}{d^2} = \sum_{d \geq 1} \frac{g(d)}{d^2} - \sum_{d > x/2} \frac{g(d)}{d^2} = G(2) + O_\varepsilon(x^{-1+\varepsilon}),$$

since

$$\sum_{d > x/2} \frac{|g(d)|}{d^2} \ll_\varepsilon x^{-1+\varepsilon}.$$

Therefore,

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \varphi_\star(n) = \frac{G(2)}{2\zeta(2)} x^2 + O_\varepsilon(x^{1+\varepsilon}).$$

Finally,

$$\frac{G(2)}{\zeta(2)} = \frac{1}{\zeta(2)} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{p-1}{p^2(p^2+p)}\right) = \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^2} + \frac{(p-1)^2}{p^5}\right) = M,$$

which gives the stated asymptotic formula. □

4.2. Summatory Order of τ_\star and Density Results for μ_\star

Recall from Theorem 1 that $\tau_\star(n) = |A(n)| = d(u(n))d(v(n))$. This function is multiplicative, and its Dirichlet series admits a factorization strong enough to yield an explicit main term with a logarithmic factor.

Theorem 9. For $\Re(s) > 1$,

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\tau_\star(n)}{n^s} = \prod_p \left(\sum_{k \geq 0} \frac{\tau_\star(p^k)}{p^{ks}} \right) = \prod_p \frac{1 + 2p^{-s}}{(1 - p^{-2s})^2},$$

where p denotes a prime. Moreover, one has the analytic factorization

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\tau_\star(n)}{n^s} = \zeta(s)^2 \zeta(2s)^2 H(s),$$

where

$$H(s) := \prod_p (1 - 3p^{-2s} + 2p^{-3s})$$

converges absolutely and defines a holomorphic function for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$. In particular, $H(s)$ is holomorphic in a neighborhood of $s = 1$ and $H(1) \neq 0$.

Proof. For p^k , where p is a prime, and k is a positive integer, write $k = 2b$ or $k = 2b + 1$. Then $u(p^{2b}) = 1$ and $v(p^{2b}) = p^b$, so $\tau_\star(p^{2b}) = d(1)d(p^b) = b + 1$. Also, $u(p^{2b+1}) = p$ and $v(p^{2b+1}) = p^b$, so $\tau_\star(p^{2b+1}) = d(p)d(p^b) = 2(b + 1)$. Hence,

$$\sum_{k \geq 0} \frac{\tau_\star(p^k)}{p^{ks}} = \sum_{b \geq 0} \frac{b + 1}{p^{2bs}} + \sum_{b \geq 0} \frac{2(b + 1)}{p^{(2b+1)s}} \tag{5}$$

$$= \frac{1}{(1 - p^{-2s})^2} + \frac{2p^{-s}}{(1 - p^{-2s})^2} \tag{6}$$

$$= \frac{1 + 2p^{-s}}{(1 - p^{-2s})^2}. \tag{7}$$

This gives the Euler product. For the factorization, write $x = p^{-s}$. Then

$$1 + 2x = (1 - x)^{-2}(1 - 3x^2 + 2x^3),$$

which is verified by multiplying the series $(1 - x)^{-2} = \sum_{n \geq 0} (n + 1)x^n$ by $1 - 3x^2 + 2x^3$ and observing that all coefficients beyond x^1 cancel. Thus,

$$\prod_p (1 + 2p^{-s}) = \prod_p (1 - p^{-s})^{-2} \prod_p (1 - 3p^{-2s} + 2p^{-3s}) = \zeta(s)^2 H(s),$$

and since $\prod_p (1 - p^{-2s})^{-2} = \zeta(2s)^2$, the claimed factorization follows. Absolute convergence of $H(s)$ for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$ follows from $\log(1 - 3p^{-2s} + 2p^{-3s}) = O(p^{-2\Re(s)})$. \square

4.3. A Sharp Asymptotic Formula for the Summatory Function of τ_\star

Lemma 1. *Let*

$$F(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{f(n)}{n^s} = \frac{\zeta(s)^2}{\zeta(2s)} G(s),$$

where $G(s)$ is holomorphic and absolutely convergent for $\Re(s) > \sigma_0$, with $\sigma_0 < \frac{1}{2}$. Then, as $x \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\sum_{n \leq x} f(n) = \frac{G(1)}{\zeta(2)} x \log x + \frac{G(1)}{\zeta(2)} \left(2\gamma - 1 + \frac{G'(1)}{G(1)} - 2 \frac{\zeta'(2)}{\zeta(2)} \right) x + O\left(x^{1/2}(\log x)^3\right).$$

Proof. This follows from the main theorem of Zhai [8] by specializing to $L(s; \chi, q) = \zeta(s)$, $M(s) = 1$, and $H(s) = 1/\zeta(s)$, together with the residue computation at $s = 1$. □

Theorem 10. *Let $\tau_\star(n) = |A(n)|$. Define*

$$A_\tau := \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{(p+1)^2} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad B_\tau := 6 \sum_p \frac{\log p}{(p-1)(p+1)(p+2)}.$$

Then, as $x \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \tau_\star(n) = A_\tau x \log x + A_\tau \left(2\gamma - 1 - B_\tau - 2 \frac{\zeta'}{\zeta}(2) \right) x + O\left(x^{1/2}(\log x)^3\right).$$

Proof. We may use the alternative factorization

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\tau_\star(n)}{n^s} = \frac{\zeta(s)^2}{\zeta(2s)} G(s),$$

where

$$G(s) := \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{2p^s + 1}{(p^s - 1)(p^s + 1)^3} \right),$$

and $G(s)$ converges absolutely in the half-plane $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{3}$. Applying Lemma 1, we obtain

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \tau_\star(n) = \frac{G(1)}{\zeta(2)} x \log x + \frac{G(1)}{\zeta(2)} \left(2\gamma - 1 + \frac{G'(1)}{G(1)} - 2 \frac{\zeta'(2)}{\zeta(2)} \right) x + O\left(x^{1/2}(\log x)^3\right).$$

Now,

$$\frac{G(1)}{\zeta(2)} = \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{(p+1)^2} \right) = A_\tau.$$

Moreover, for each prime p the Euler factor of $G(s)$ is

$$G_p(s) = 1 + \frac{2p^s + 1}{(p^s - 1)(p^s + 1)^3},$$

so a direct differentiation gives

$$-\frac{G'_p(1)}{G_p(1)} = \frac{6 \log p}{(p - 1)(p + 1)(p + 2)}.$$

Summing over primes yields

$$-\frac{G'(1)}{G(1)} = 6 \sum_p \frac{\log p}{(p - 1)(p + 1)(p + 2)} = B_\tau.$$

Substituting these identities completes the proof. □

Theorem 11. *One has $\mu_\star(n) \neq 0$ if and only if $\nu_p(n) \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ for every prime p . In particular, the set*

$$\mathcal{S} := \{n \in \mathbb{N} : \mu_\star(n) \neq 0\}$$

has natural density

$$\delta(\mathcal{S}) = \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^4}\right) = \frac{1}{\zeta(4)}.$$

Equivalently,

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \mu_\star(n)^2 \sim \frac{1}{\zeta(4)} x.$$

Proof. By Theorem 3, $\mu_\star(n) = \mu(u(n))\mu(v(n))$. Since $u(n)$ is squarefree, $\mu(u(n)) \neq 0$ always. Thus, $\mu_\star(n) \neq 0$ if and only if $\mu(v(n)) \neq 0$. That is, $\mu_\star(n) \neq 0$ if and only if $v(n)$ is squarefree. Now

$$v(n) = \prod_p p^{\lfloor \nu_p(n)/2 \rfloor}$$

is squarefree if and only if $\lfloor \nu_p(n)/2 \rfloor \in \{0, 1\}$ for all p . Equivalently, it is squarefree if and only if $\nu_p(n) \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ for all p .

For the density, the local condition at a prime p is $\nu_p(n) \leq 3$. The probability that a random integer has $\nu_p(n) = k$ is $(1 - 1/p)p^{-k}$. Hence, the local contribution equals

$$\sum_{k=0}^3 (1 - 1/p)p^{-k} = (1 - 1/p) \frac{1 - p^{-4}}{1 - p^{-1}} = 1 - p^{-4}.$$

Independence over primes gives $\delta(\mathcal{S}) = \prod_p (1 - p^{-4}) = 1/\zeta(4)$. Finally, $\mu_\star(n)^2$ is the indicator function of \mathcal{S} , hence the asserted asymptotic follows. □

5. Numerical Examples

In Table 1, we list $u(n)$, $v(n)$, the A -divisor count $\tau_*(n)$, $\mu_*(n)$, and $\varphi_*(n)$ for $1 \leq n \leq 12$.

n	$(u(n), v(n))$	$\tau_*(n)$	$\mu_*(n)$	$\varphi_*(n)$
1	(1, 1)	1	1	1
2	(2, 1)	2	-1	1
3	(3, 1)	2	-1	2
4	(1, 2)	2	-1	3
5	(5, 1)	2	-1	4
6	(6, 1)	4	+1	2
7	(7, 1)	2	-1	6
8	(2, 2)	4	+1	3
9	(1, 3)	2	-1	8
10	(10, 1)	4	+1	4
11	(11, 1)	2	-1	10
12	(3, 2)	4	+1	6

Table 1: Values of $u(n)$, $v(n)$, $\tau_*(n)$, $\mu_*(n)$, and $\varphi_*(n)$ for $1 \leq n \leq 12$.

As a consistency check, for $n = 12$ we have $A(12) = \{1, 4, 3, 12\}$, and indeed,

$$\varphi_*(1) + \varphi_*(4) + \varphi_*(3) + \varphi_*(12) = 1 + 3 + 2 + 6 = 12.$$

To illustrate Theorem 8, we compare the ratio

$$\frac{1}{x^2} \sum_{n \leq x} \varphi_*(n)$$

with the predicted constant $M/2 \approx 0.3254359793$. Empirically,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{50^2} \sum_{n \leq 50} \varphi_*(n) &= 0.3336, \\ \frac{1}{200^2} \sum_{n \leq 200} \varphi_*(n) &= 0.3275, \\ \frac{1}{20000^2} \sum_{n \leq 20000} \varphi_*(n) &= 0.3254425, \end{aligned}$$

which is consistent with convergence to $M/2$.

6. Conclusion

We introduced a concrete square–splitting divisor system $A(n)$ and its induced A -convolution \star . The key structural result is the ring isomorphism with a two-variable Dirichlet convolution, which yields explicit and computable arithmetic: a closed formula for μ_\star , a sharp inversion theorem, Euler products for generalized divisor sums, and a new Euler-type totient φ_\star with exact prime-power values. This fits into the general divisor-system convolution framework initiated by Narkiewicz and developed further in related settings such as unitary and cross-convolutions [5, 2, 7].

We also established an effective asymptotic formula for $\sum_{n \leq x} \varphi_\star(n)$, whose leading constant is given by a simple absolutely convergent Euler product. In addition, we obtained a sharp asymptotic formula for $\sum_{n \leq x} \tau_\star(n)$ and determined the natural density of the support of μ_\star . These results show that the square–splitting convolution admits a tractable analytic theory alongside its explicit algebraic structure.

Further questions include possible refinements and extensions of the asymptotic theory for $\sum_{n \leq x} \tau_\star(n)$, as well as related distributional problems for $\mu_\star(n)$ and other arithmetic functions associated with this convolution; see also the analytic tools used in [6, 1].

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